

Supplementary information

1. Ahmadabad, Razavi Khorasan Province, 35°09'05.7"N 59°17'01.7"E
2. Deh Gheibi, Razavi Khorasan Province, 36°08'31.4"N 59°30'43.5"E
3. Shurak Maleki, Razavi Khorasan Province, 36°05'36.0"N 60°11'15.5"E
4. Dizbad Bala, Razavi Khorasan Province, 36°08'32.6"N 59°19'24.3"E
5. Chang Abad, Razavi Khorasan Province, 35°22'59.1"N 60°42'15.8"E
6. Ab Daraz, Bazangan lake entrance, Razavi Khorasan Province, 36°18'31.6"N 60°29'00.4"E
7. Bazangan lake, Razavi Khorasan Province, 36°18'51.4"N 60°28'40.3"E
8. Haft Houz Valley, Razavi Khorasan Province, 36°11'46.2"N 59°32'56.1"E
9. Shurak Maleki, Razavi Khorasan Province, 36°05'36.0"N 60°11'15.5"E
10. Aq Kariz, Razavi Khorasan Province, 37°09'05.4"N 58°32'27.3"E
11. Torbat-e-jam, Razavi Khorasan Province 35°13'26.7"N 60°24'04.0"E
12. Parvand, Razavi Khorasan Province, 35°53'51.0"N 57°03'35.3"E
13. Kalateh-ye Mirza Jani, Razavi Khorasan Province, 36°06'40.2"N 60°07'29.1"E
14. Haft Houz Valley, Razavi Khorasan Province, 36°11'43.9"N 59°32'53.5"E
15. Haft Houz Valley, Razavi Khorasan Province, 36°11'24.1"N 59°33'22.3"E
16. Haft Houz Valley, Razavi Khorasan Province, 36°11'43.5"N 59°32'53.1"E
17. Haft Houz Valley, Razavi Khorasan Province, 36°19'54.2"N 59°54'80.8"E
18. Torbat Heydariyeh, Razavi Khorasan Province, 35°15'51.3"N 59°17'42.9"E
19. Rivash, Razavi Khorasan Province, 35°34'16.0"N 58°25'27.9"E
20. Joveyn, Razavi Khorasan Province, 36°39'18.0"N 57°29'53.5"E
21. Rivash, Razavi Khorasan Province, 35°34'20.0"N 58°25'30.4"E
22. Neyshabur, Razavi Khorasan Province, 35°33'55.9"N 58°25'33.2"E
23. Bahramieh, Joveyn, Razavi Khorasan Province, 36°39'00.7"N 57°30'42.3"E
24. Mashkan, Razavi Khorasan Province, 36°29'45.1"N 58°08'28.3"E
25. Amirabad, Kalat, Razavi Khorasan Province, 36°32'45.2"N 60°09'18.7"E
26. Bahramieh, Joveyn, Razavi Khorasan Province, 36°38'47.2"N 57°30'43.5"E
27. Chah-E Shur, Iran, Razavi Khorasan Province, 34°56'46.8"N 60°55'48.1"E
28. Sonj, Bashrooye, Razavi Khorasan Province, 33°32'06.2"N 57°21'11"